

Workshop: RDMO for Editors

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Agenda

Day 1 - Basics for Editors

- RDMO roles, elements & hierarchy
- Catalog, Sections & Pages
 - **Hands-On**
- Questions settings & formats
 - **Hands-On**

– Break –

- Attributes
 - **Hands-On**

– Break –

- OptionSets and Options
 - **Hands-On**

Wrap Up & Feedback

Day 2 - NFDI DMP Template Framework

- Welcome & Recap Day 1
- Collections
 - **Hands-On**
- Conditions
 - **Hands-On**

– Break –

- NFDI DMP Template Framework (Part I)
 - **Hands-On**

– Break –

- NFDI DMP Template Framework (Part II)
 - **Hands-On**

Wrap Up & Feedback

Collections

Hands-on: Collections

Collections

Exercise 5 - Collections

- Explore: What happens when adding attributes to pages or question sets?
 - Use attribute “`.../dataset/id`” for a page
 - Use attribute “`.../partner/id`” for a question set
- Tip
 - There is one more setting you will need!

Collections

Pages as collections

- User perspective

Collections

Pages as collections

- Management perspective
 - Add attribute to page (commonly used “dataset/id” and similar)
 - Mark page as “is collection”

The screenshot displays a hierarchical metadata structure with three levels:

- Section: Data Description** (count: 1)
 - URL: <https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/questions/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/Dataset>
- Page: Content Data Description** (count: 0)
 - URL: https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/questions/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/DMP/Dataset/data_description_content
 - URL: <https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/domain/project/dataset/id>
- Question: What kind of dataset is it?** (count: 0)
 - URL: https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/questions/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/DMP/Dataset/rdadmp_title
 - URL: <https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/domain/project/dataset/description>

Collections

Question sets as collections

- User perspective

Responsibilities

Who is responsible for the adequate handling of the research data (description of the roles and responsibilities within the project)?

Possible roles are, e.g. project leader, data collector, data manager, data steward. You can find more examples on the [Harvard Medical School RDM Website](#)

Please enter your entries block by block. You can add blocks using the green button and remove them using the blue cross (x).

+ Block

Responsibilities

Who is responsible for the adequate handling of the research data (description of the roles and responsibilities within the project)?

Possible roles are, e.g. project leader, data collector, data manager, data steward. You can find more examples on the [Harvard Medical School RDM Website](#)

Please enter your entries block by block. You can add blocks using the green button and remove them using the blue cross (x).

Who is responsible for the adequate handling of the research data (description of the roles and responsibilities within the project)?

First name:

Family name:

Affiliation:

ORCID:

E-Mail:

Phone number:

Role in the project:

+ Block

Collections

Question sets as collections

- Management perspective
 - Add attribute to question (e.g. “person/id”)
 - Mark question as “is collection”

The screenshot displays a hierarchical structure of question sets and questions in the RDMO system. It consists of four main components:

- Section:** "Responsibilities and resources" with a URL `https://rdmo.nfdi4ing.de/terms/questions/NFDI4Ing_Vorlage/v2/responsibilities` and a count of 6. It includes edit, share, and lock icons.
- Page:** "Responsibilities" with a URL `https://rdmo.nfdi4ing.de/terms/questions/NFDI4Ing_Vorlage/v2/responsibilities/responsibilities` and a count of 0. It also includes edit, share, and lock icons.
- Question set:** "Who is responsible for the adequate handling of the research data (description of the roles and responsibilities within the project)?" with a URL `https://rdmo.nfdi4ing.de/terms/questions/v2/responsibilities/responsibilities/datahandling` and a count of 1. It includes a red URL `https://rdmo.nfdi4ing.de/terms/domain/project_responsible_person_id`.
- Question:** "Who is responsible for the adequate handling of the research data (description of the roles and responsibilities within the project)?" with a URL `https://rdmo.nfdi4ing.de/terms/questions/NFDI4Ing_Vorlage/v2/responsibilities/responsibilities/datahandling_person` and a count of 0. It includes two red URLs: `https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/domain/project/dataset/pids/responsible_person` and `https://rdmo.nfdi4ing.de/terms/options/v2/NFDI_responsible_person`.

Conditions

Overview of the RDMO Hierarchy

- **Catalog:** top-level container of your DMP template
 - **Section:** Major divisions within the Catalog containing pages
 - **Page:** subdivisions of a section containing questions or question sets
 - **Question sets:** group of related questions within a page, e.g. responsible(s) for handling data
 - **Questions**
 - **Questions**
 - **Option sets:** a predefined group of answer choices used for questions
 - **Options:** the components of Option sets

Conditions

Introduction

- Goal: hide questions that are not relevant for the user
- Content element is visible only, if the condition is met
 - A list of conditions is evaluated as logical OR

Conditions

SMP Catalog

- Software Management Plan Catalog V.3.0
 - https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/blob/main/rdmorganiser/questions/SMP_Readme.md
 - <https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/blob/main/rdmorganiser/questions/questions-smp.xml>
- Developed by Max Planck Digital Library
 - Version 3 co-developed with NFDI4ING

The screenshot shows the DMP4nfdi web interface. The top navigation bar includes 'DMP4nfdi', 'Back to project', 'Management', 'Demo Instance', and 'Fee'. The breadcrumb trail is 'My Projects / SMP Test / General'. The form contains the following sections:

- Topic**: A text area with a help icon. Text: "If you are looking for an introduction to the topic before completing a software management plan, then we recommend Martinez-Ortiz et al. (2022): Practical guide to Software Management Plans, v1.0, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7589725>."
- What is the title of the software project?**: A text area with a help icon. Text: "The title of the software can, of course, still change or be specified in the course of a project. Nevertheless, it makes sense to give the project a specific name at the beginning in order to facilitate further (internal) communication about it."
- Which research field(s) does this software belong to?**: A text area with a help icon. Text: "The list of disciplines follows the subject classification of the DFG (German Research Foundation). Please enter your entries line by line. You can add lines using the green button and remove them using the blue cross (x)."
- In which application class is the software categorised?**: A text area with a help icon. Text: "The application classes are essentially based on the 'DLR Software Engineering Guidelines' (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1344612>), p. 7-8. Depending on the selection in this questions a selection of different questions is provided below." A link: "Click here for more information on the application classes for research software".

The 'Application Class 2' radio button is selected.

Conditions

SMP Catalog

Application Class

Class 0

Class 1

Class 2

Class 3

Topic	Project Partners	Project Schedule	Project Management
Development Requirements	Code	Third Party Components	Infrastructure
Preservation	Security	Governance	Documentation
Testing	Releasing	Public Availability	Metadata
Support	Intellectual Property Rights	License	Dual Use

Conditions

SMP Catalog

Application Class

Class 0

Class 1

Class 2

Class 3

Topic	Project Partners	Project Schedule	Project Management
Development Requirements	Code	Third Party Components	Infrastructure
Preservation	Security	Governance	Documentation
Testing	Releasing	Public Availability	Metadata
Support	Intellectual Property Rights	License	Dual Use

Conditions

SMP Catalog

Application Class

Class 0

Class 1

Class 2

Class 3

Topic	Project Partners	Project Schedule	Project Management
Development Requirements	Code	Third Party Components	Infrastructure
Preservation	Security	Governance	Documentation
Testing	Releasing	Public Availability	Metadata
Support	Intellectual Property Rights	License	Dual Use

Conditions

SMP Catalog

Application Class

Class 0

Class 1

Class 2

Class 3

Topic	Project Partners	Project Schedule	Project Management
Development Requirements	Code	Third Party Components	Infrastructure
Preservation	Security	Governance	Documentation
Testing	Releasing	Public Availability	Metadata
Support	Intellectual Property Rights	License	Dual Use

Conditions

Introduction

- User perspective

In which application class is the software categorised?

The application classes are essentially based on the "DLR Software Engineering Guidelines" (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1344612>), p. 7-8. Depending on the selection in this questions a selection of different questions is provided below.

▶ [Click here for more information on the application classes for research software](#)

- Application class 0: The focus of the software is on personal use in conjunction with a small scope. The distribution of the software within and outside the own institution is not planned.
- Application Class 1: The software is only develop within a narrow scope. It is to be further developed and used beyond personal purposes.
- Application Class 2: The software is intended to ensure long-term development and maintainability. It is the basis for a transition to product status.
- Application Class 3: For the software it is essential to avoid errors and to reduce risks. This applies in particular to critical software and that with product characteristics.

Progress

 1 of 9

[Back](#)

[Proceed](#)

Navigation

Grey entries will be conditionally skipped based on your input.

[General \(1 of 5\)](#)

[Technical](#)

[Quality Assurance](#)

Governance and Defined Processes

→ [Documentation](#)

Testing

[Release and Publish](#)

[Legal and Ethics](#)

Conditions

Introduction

- Management perspective
 - Open a question, option set, ...
 - Add existing or create new conditions

Page: Third Party Components and Libraries ⌵ 🔗 + 🔒 📄 +

<https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/questions/smp/technical/components> 1

Question: Which external software components will be used? What dependencies on software libraries do exist? How do you document this? 🔗 🔒 📄 +

<https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/conditions/application-class-1>

<https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/conditions/application-class-2>

<https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/conditions/application-class-3>

Question: What licences are on the third-party software components? 🔗 🔒 📄 +

<https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/conditions/application-class-2>

<https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/conditions/application-class-3>

Conditions Option sets Range Default Editors

Conditions

<https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/conditions/application-class-1> ⌵ 🔗 ✕

<https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/conditions/application-class-2> ⌵ 🔗 ✕

<https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/conditions/application-class-3> ⌵ 🔗 ✕

[Add existing condition](#) [Create new condition](#)

List of conditions evaluated for this question.

Conditions

How to create a new condition

- Management > Conditions

The screenshot displays the 'Management' interface for conditions. At the top, there is a 'Conditions' header with 'Back' and 'New' buttons. Below this is a search bar labeled 'Filter conditions' and a dropdown menu showing the current URL 'https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/t/'. To the right of the search bar is a dropdown menu for 'All editors'. The main content area lists seven conditions, each with a URL and a set of action icons (edit, lock, delete). A red arrow points to the 'New' button in the top right corner of the conditions list. On the right side, there is a 'Navigation' sidebar with a list of menu items: Catalogs, Sections, Pages, Question sets, Questions, Attributes, Option sets, Options, Conditions, Tasks, and Views. The 'Conditions' item is highlighted with a red box. Below the navigation sidebar is an 'Export' section with the text 'Export all visible elements.' and a list of export formats: XML, XML (full), PDF, Rich Text Format, Open Office, Microsoft Office, HTML, Markdown, mediawiki, and LaTeX.

Condition	URL	Actions
Condition:	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/conditions/dmp4nfdi_v1-0-0_contributor_backups	✎ 🔒 🗑️
Condition:	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/conditions/dmp4nfdi_v1-0-0_contributor_datamanagement	✎ 🔒 🗑️
Condition:	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/conditions/dmp4nfdi_v1-0-0_contributor_metadata	✎ 🔒 🗑️
Condition:	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/conditions/dmp4nfdi_v1-0-0_contributor_pid	✎ 🔒 🗑️
Condition:	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/conditions/dmp4nfdi_v1-0-0_contributor_preservation	✎ 🔒 🗑️
Condition:	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/conditions/dmp4nfdi_v1-0-0_control_tool	✎ 🔒 🗑️
Condition:	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/conditions/dmp4nfdi_v1-0-0_personnel_data_deletion	✎ 🔒 🗑️

Conditions

How to create a new condition

- Source: Attribute that is evaluated
- Relation: defines how the attribute's value is compared
- Target options
 - A) Text
 - B) Option
- Yes/No questions: use Target (Text) with value 1 (Yes) or 0 (No)

Management

Create condition Back Create and continue editing Create

URI Prefix ✎
The prefix for the URI of this condition.

URI Path
The path for the URI of this condition.

Comment

Additional internal information about this condition.

Locked
Designates whether this condition can be changed.

Source

Create new attribute
The attribute of the value for this condition.

Relation
 x v
The relation this condition is using.

Target (Text)

If using a regular value, the text value this condition is checking against (for boolean values use 1 and 0).

Target (Option)

If using a value pointing to an option, the option this condition is checking against.

Editors
 x v
The sites that can edit this condition (in a multi site setup).

Back Create and continue editing Create

Hands-on: Conditions

Conditions

Exercise 6 - Conditions

- Create a condition targeting an option and add it to your catalog
- Tip
 - Not all relations work for Target(OPTION)

Management

Create condition Back Create and continue editing Create

URI Prefix ✎

The prefix for the URI of this condition.

URI Path

The path for the URI of this condition.

Comment

Additional internal information about this condition.

Locked

Designates whether this condition can be changed.

Source

Create new attribute

The attribute of the value for this condition.

Relation

x v

The relation this condition is using.

Target (Text)

If using a regular value, the text value this condition is checking against (for boolean values use 1 and 0).

Target (Option)

If using a value pointing to an option, the option this condition is checking against.

Editors

x v

The sites that can edit this condition (in a multi site setup).

Back Create and continue editing Create

Conditions

Summary

- With conditions you can hide questions that are not relevant for the user
- You can assign conditions to questions, question sets, pages, or sections
- Conditions either target text or specific options
- A list of conditions is evaluated as logical OR

Management

Create condition Back Create and continue editing Create

URI Prefix ✎ **URI Path**

The prefix for the URI of this condition. The path for the URI of this condition.

Comment

Additional internal information about this condition.

Locked
Designates whether this condition can be changed.

Source

Create new attribute

The attribute of the value for this condition.

Relation

x ▼

The relation this condition is using.

Target (Text)

If using a regular value, the text value this condition is checking against (for boolean values use 1 and 0).

Target (Option)

If using a value pointing to an option, the option this condition is checking against.

Editors

x ▼

The sites that can edit this condition (in a multi site setup).

Back Create and continue editing Create

The NFDI DMP Template Framework

The NFDI DMP Template Framework

Problem:

- no standards
- Same attributes for different questions
- Same questions with different attributes
- Difficult to find the right attribute vs. Easy to create a new attribute

Our Goal

Ensure Interoperability across NFDI DMP Templates and enable integration with services (maDMP)

- Background of DMP4NFDI & the TF
- Method how we developed it
- Explanations of elements within the TF
- Recommendations on how to use it
- Workflow to implement

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16737079>

The NFDI DMP Template Framework

RDA DMP Common Standard for machine-actionable Data Management Plans

- ➔ metadata application profile to provide basic interoperability between systems
- ➔ represents information over the whole DMP lifecycle

<https://github.com/RDA-DMP-Common/RDA-DMP-Common-Standard>

Entities cluster the informations belonging to each other
Properties specify each information in an entity by providing standardised names

They form the basis of the mapping to the RDMO attributes

Structure

- dmp
 - contact
 - affiliation
 - contact_id
 - identifier
 - type
 - mbox
 - name
 - contributor
 - affiliation
 - contributor_id
 - identifier
 - type
 - mbox
 - name
 - role
 - cost
 - currency_code
 - description
 - title
 - value
 - created
 - dataset
 - creator
 - affiliation
 - creator_id
 - identifier
 - type
 - mbox
 - name
 - data_quality_assurance

The NFDI DMP Template Framework

- Structure**
- [dmp](#)
 - [contact](#)
 - [affiliation](#)
 - [contact_id](#)
 - [identifier](#)
 - [type](#)
 - [mbox](#)
 - [name](#)
 - [contributor](#)
 - [affiliation](#)
 - [contributor_id](#)
 - [identifier](#)
 - [type](#)
 - [mbox](#)
 - [name](#)
 - [role](#)
 - [cost](#)
 - [currency_code](#)
 - [description](#)
 - [title](#)
 - [value](#)
 - [created](#)
 - [dataset](#)
 - [creator](#)
 - [affiliation](#)
 - [creator_id](#)
 - [identifier](#)
 - [type](#)
 - [mbox](#)
 - [name](#)
 - [data_quality_assurance](#)

RDMO Attribute
project/dataset/sharing/repository
project/dataset/sharing/restrictions_explanation
project/dataset/pids/system
project/dataset/storage/type
project/dataset/versioning/tool
project/dataset/data_security/backups

Attributes in RDMO are the storage location for the information entered by users and can be accessed via interfaces. By looking at the attribute we can also find the related questions.

Question	Type	Obligation	RDA maDMP Property	RDMO Attribute
Who is the main contact person for questions related to data management?	String	mandatory	rdadmp:dmp/contact/name	project/data_management/name

For **standardisation and interoperability** we defined:

- Scope of the attribute
- Obligation
- Type

The NFDI DMP Template Framework

Used mappings in the RDMO "NFDI DMP Template"

- questions from existing RDMO catalogs adjusted with focus groups
- optionsets from existing catalogs, the RDA maDMP or consortia needs
- plugins from the RDMO community or consortia needs

The NFDI DMP Template Framework

Navigation

Using the navigation will save your input.

Grey entries will be conditionally skipped based on your input.

General Information

→ General Project Informations

Project Funding

General DMP Information

Legal Restrictions regarding the ...

Responsibilities and Resources

Data Description

Documentation and Data Quality

Storage and technical Archiving dur...

Data Exchange and long-term Data...

Legal obligations and conditions

The NFDI DMP Template Framework

Work with RDMO community

- Keep track of the attribute domain
- Integrate naming conventions for attributes or URI paths
- Stay up to date with software developments: user interface, plugins, recommendations

Discussions in workshops

- Fine-tune overall topics with the RDM community

Work with consortia

- Start of integration phase with 5 incubator projects:
 - ❖ Text+, 4Culture, 4Objects, FAIRagro, 4Memory
- Reuse of the TF so far by: FAIRagro, Text+, (4Memory)
- Adapt features relevant for all

Work with focus groups

- Define legal questions with service stuart
- Stronger focus on digital preservation with LTA group
- Integrations of pids with PID4NFDI

- Stay up to date with new initiatives

The NFDI DMP Template Framework

The NFDI DMP Template is publicly available at the RDMO repository.

The image shows two overlapping screenshots. The left screenshot is the 'DMP4nfdi' management interface, displaying a 'Katalog: NFDI DMP Template' with various filters and sections like 'Abschnitt: Allgemeine Informationen' and 'Seite: Allgemeine Projektinformationen'. The right screenshot is a GitHub repository view for 'rdmorganiser / rdmo-catalog', showing the file structure under 'shared / DMP4NFDI /' with files like '2025-06-26_dmp4nfdi_v1-0-0.xml' and 'NFDI_DMP_Template.md'. A commit message 'jwindeck Update shared/DMP4NFDI/NFDI_DMP_Template.md' is visible.

<https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/tree/main/shared/DMP4NFDI>

You can reuse and edit it, but we are **happy to know** 😊

Hands-on: NFDI DMP Template Framework

The NFDI DMP Template Framework

Exercise 7

Create a copy of the TF catalog with your own URI Prefix

DEMO

The NFDI DMP Template

The NFDI DMP Template Framework

Why using the TF?

Initial users of the TF:

- Text+
- NFDI4Objects
- NFDI4Memory?
- FAIRagro

NFDI DMP

The NFDI DMP Template Framework

Work with
FAIRagro

NFDI DMP Template 4 FAIRagro

- General Information
 - General Project Information
 - Project Funding
- General DMP Information
- Legal Restrictions regarding the ...
→ Responsibilities and Resources
- Data Description
- Documentation and Data Quality
- Storage during the Project
- Data Exchange and long-term Data...
- Legal obligations and conditions

Who is responsible for adequate handling of the research data (description of roles and responsibilities within the project)?

Please enter your entries block by block. You can add blocks using the green button and remove them using the blue cross (*).

Name	ORCID	ROR
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Role

- Data Steward
- Project Manager
- Data Analyst
- Data Owner
- Data Collector
- Other:

+ BLOCK

What standards, ontologies, classifications, etc. are used to describe the data and contextual information?

Comprehensive data descriptions enhance the usability, interpretation, and reuse of data. Well-established metadata standards and ontologies support consistent structuring and documentation of data, thereby promoting interoperability and facilitating scientific collaboration.

We recommend using established standards, ontologies, controlled vocabularies, and metadata schemas for your data description. Whenever possible, align with subject-specific guidelines or the requirements of relevant repositories for data deposition after project completion.

For more information on subject-specific metadata standards and ontologies, please refer to the FAIRagro Standard Inventory.

Other option:

- ICASA
- MIAPPE
- OGC SensorThings API
- MCPD
- EPPO codes
- Crop ontology
- PPEO ontology
- Plant trait ontology
- SOSA/SSN ontology

Additional questions
from Horizon Europe

The NFDI DMP Template Framework

Refining the TF:

- AG LTA
- PID
- Legal Issues
- get in touch with us!

Staying interoperable:

- use the attribute mapping for your plugins
- reuse and refine the NFDI DMP Template

Get in touch with us!

Hands-on: NFDI DMP Template (Part I)

The NFDI DMP Template Framework

Exercise 8

Look through the catalog NFDI DMP Template (not your copy!), where are questions that you might want to adapt?

Collect your findings

break

Hands-on: NFDI DMP Template (Part II)

The NFDI DMP Template Framework

Exercise 9

adapt 1 option set to your needs

DEMO

Wrap-up & Feedback

RDMO Elements & NFDI DMP Template

The NFDI DMP Template Framework

Version: 1.0.0

Next steps with RDMO

From a user's perspective to an editor's perspective

Our recommendations

Adapt the NFDI DMP template to your discipline needs

Integrate RDMO with services relevant to your consortium/discipline

Raise awareness of data/software management planning within your consortium by showcasing the value of RDMO

DMP4NFDI

Call for incubator projects 01/2026

First call for incubators opens on **Nov 17, 2025**.

An incubator project is a short-term engagement (3–6 months) with a clearly defined goal. Typical focus areas include:

Hosting
&
Integration with other services

Template standardisation
&
Support for development

Training
&
Support for outreach

DMP4NFDI

Call for incubator projects 01/2026

Interested?

Complete the [short application template](#) outlining your goals, team, and expected outcomes, and **submit the template by Dec 15.**

You'll find the template here:

<https://dmp.services.base4nfdi.de/incubator/#call>

You have ideas and would like to discuss them? **Contact us!**

<https://dmp.services.base4nfdi.de/contact/>

Have a look at our current incubators projects:

<https://dmp.services.base4nfdi.de/incubator/#incubators>

Feedback

From a user's perspective to an editor's perspective

How was working with RDMO and the NFDI DMP Template?

What did you like about today?

What can be improved?

